
TRANSLATION TECHNIQUES TO ANALYSE DIFFERENT TYPES OF TEXTS

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Annotation.

This article is interpreted on the basis of the issues of general linguistic description of translation procedures. It expresses features as the translation, strategies, sentences, range of perspectives and have been assigned a multitude of labels, among which we have procedures, techniques, strategies, processes and methods. the type of text, the purpose of the translation and the nature of the readers and words in translation of meaning on the logical basis of lexemes.

Keywords.

fragmentation, homogeneous, translation procedure, comparative stylistics, systematic practice, translator's reach, empirical translator, manner of mistakes.

Introduction

Amplification vs. Economy. Amplification occurs when the TL uses more signifiers to cover syntactic or lexical gaps. Amplification is often required in technical and academic texts as an aid to assure a better understanding of the original message or to decode certain ST elements, whose linguistic, semantic or cultural equivalents may not be clear enough in the TT. According to Vinay and Darbelnet, dissolution is a question of langue and adaptation of parole. The opposite procedure is economy, which implies the reduction of the number of words used in the translation of the TT. A translation is considered economical, when the same content of the ST is expressed more concisely and with a shorter number of elements in the target text. The amplification is applied by using more words in the target text to cover syntactic or lexical gaps. This procedure also covers completion or lengthening, where a target-text word grammatically needs the support of another word.

Reinforcement vs. Condensation. Characteristic examples of reinforcement are English prepositions and conjunctions that tend to be supplemented in French by the use of nouns or verbs.

Explication vs. Implication. Explication is to introduce information from the ST that is implicit from the context or the situation, e.g., to make explicit the patient's sex when translating his patient into French. Implication is to allow the situation to indicate information that is explicit in the ST, e.g., the meaning of *sortez* as go out or come out depends on the situation.

Materials And Methods

Generalization vs. Particularization. Generalization is to translate a term for a more general one, whereas, particularization is the opposite. These translation techniques are frequently used to adjust structural and stylistic differences between source and target language texts and also as a tool to influence and shape the audience's understanding of reality. An example of generalization is the translation of *rose, orchid and tulip* by *flowers* or *hammer, drill and screwdriver* by *tools*. And good examples of particularization are the colloquial expressions for medical terms, that can be more precisely translated *stomach inflammation* by *gastritis* or *eye infection* by *conjunctivitis*.

Inversion is used when there is need to move a word or a phrase to another place in a sentence or a paragraph so that it reads naturally in the target language. It implies the alteration of the word order or the phrase structure in a sentence or a paragraph in order to achieve a more natural emphasis or to reveal specific stylistic characteristics in the target text. And with the description of these twelve complementary translation strategies, we conclude this section and the seven translation procedures first proposed in 1958 by Vinay and Darbelnet would be completed. Translation has been used to transfer written or spoken source language texts to equivalent written or spoken target language texts. In general, the purpose of translation is to reproduce various kinds of texts-including religious, literary, scientific, and philosophical texts-in another language and thus making them available to wider readers. If language were just a classification for a set of general or universal concepts, it would be easy to translate from an SL to a TL; furthermore, under the circumstances the process of learning an L2 would be much easier than it actually is.

One of the problems of translation is the disparity among world languages. The bigger the gap between the source language and the target language, the more difficult the transfer of message from the former to the latter will be. In order to simplify and make the translation strategies described visually more accessible.

Result And Discussion

Translation can be understood as the process of transferring a text from a source language to a target language. A translation theorist Susan Bassnett stated that “nowadays, translating is a common human condition, and the rapid increase of media causes a rise in the importance of translation”⁵⁵. Translation is a crucial part of knowledge transfer. If a research paper is not translated properly, the process of knowledge transferring may be disrupted. A paper that is not written in English must be translated into English if the writer wishes it to get published in international journals. Any work that is translated with poor translation may hinder it from being discovered and read by many people, as well as getting published in international publication. In relation to translation, translation techniques have been proposed by researchers in this field. Molina and Albir in 2002 proposed “18 classifications of translation techniques”. The techniques are adaptation, amplification, borrowing, calque, compensation, description, discursive creation, established equivalent, generalization, linguistic amplification, linguistic compression, literal translation, modulation, particularization, reduction, substitution, transposition, and variation.

Conclusion

These translation techniques were derived from existing techniques of translations proposed by other experts such as Nida’s “translation theory”⁵⁷ and Newmark’s “translation methods”⁵⁸. The translation techniques were developed because the methods, strategies, and techniques need to be further distinguished and the due to the need of functional concept of translation techniques. Several works and researches have been conducted with Molina and Albir’s translation techniques to analyse the information. Scholars analyzed the translation a movie script using the techniques. The findings of their study showed that linguistic compression was used the most prominently while other techniques occurred less frequently. Another research was conducted to investigate the translation of cultural words. This research revealed that pure borrowing occurs the most, followed by transposition, while the rest occurred less times. Studies show that there is a huge gap between the use of a translation technique that was used the most and the rest of the techniques. Not only literature texts, but the translation techniques have also been used for example to analyze religious texts a well. A research conducted to analyze religious tourism brochure and in the study, it was revealed that translation techniques that were used the most in translating the brochures to English were pure borrowing and there are a few others that appeared significantly less.

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